

Eco2adapt survey about future forests and their management practices.

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Welcome to our questionnaire!

Thank you for participating in this questionnaire, which aims to provide insight into how future ecological and socioeconomic changes will affect forests and their management.

The questionnaire consists of two main parts, which deal separately with the effects of future ecological and socioeconomic changes. For each part, we present you with current data specific to your region. We ask you to evaluate the data and give us your assessment of possible changes. Some questions may be difficult to answer, but we ask you to answer all questions, as your assessment of the changes is important for our research.

In addition, we would like to hear your opinion on the presentation of the data in order to understand how the future impacts of climate change on forests and their management can best be communicated.

Furthermore, we will discuss adaptation strategies in terms of both ecological and economic resilience.

Your answers are anonymous, will be treated confidentially, and will be used solely for research purposes. We will, of course, make the results available to you on the eco2adapt homepage.

We thank you for your participation in this questionnaire, which is important for decision-making in the forestry sector and the future adaptation of forests.

Personal information

At first, we kindly ask you to provide us with your personal information.

* Please specify your fields of profession in the context to the forest in your region.

Forest manager

- Forest owner
- Forest worker
- Wood sales & wood processing
- Environmental education
- Nature conservation
- Forest research
- Hunting or fishing
- Policy maker
- Recreation and tourism
- Other

Other, please specify

* Please specify your affiliations in the context of the forest in your region.

- State agency
- Province agency
- Municipality agency
- Forest Management Association
- Private person
- Private company
- NGO
- Association (e.g., recreation, hunting)
- University or research institute
- Other

Other, please specify

Please indicate how much experience you have in your professional field (in years).

- 0-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 15+

Objectives

In your opinion, what are the most important objectives the forest management in your region should focus on?
You can select up to 5 (Objective 1 is the most important).

* Objective 1:

- Timber production
- Nature protection
- Provision of recreation, leisure and tourism
- Pollution control (water, air and soil)
- Erosion control
- Water provision
- Climate change mitigation by carbon storage in biomass
- Biodiversity & habitat for wildlife
- Provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, hunting)
- Grazing and other agroforestry
- Protection against natural hazard (e.g., floods, avalanches, rockfall)
- Education
- Other

Other, please specify

Objective 2:

- Timber production
- Nature protection
- Pollution control (water, air and soil)
- Erosion control
- Water provision
- Climate change mitigation by carbon storage in biomass
- Biodiversity & habitat for wildlife
- Grazing and other agroforestry
- Provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, hunting)
- Education
- Other
- Protection against natural hazard (e.g., floods, avalanches, rockfall)
- Protection against natural hazards (e.g. floods, avalanches, rock falls)
- Education
- Others

Other, please specify

Objective 3:

- Timber production
- Nature protection

- Pollution control (water, air and soil)
- Erosion control
- Water provision
- Climate change mitigation by carbon storage in biomass
- Biodiversity & habitat for wildlife
- Grazing and other agroforestry
- Provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, hunting)
- Education
- Other
- Protection against natural hazard (e.g., floods, avalanches, rockfall)
- Protection against natural hazards (e.g. floods, avalanches, rock falls)
- Education
- Others

Other, please specify

Objective 4:

- Timber production
- Nature protection
- Pollution control (water, air and soil)
- Erosion control
- Water provision
- Climate change mitigation by carbon storage in biomass
- Biodiversity & habitat for wildlife
- Grazing and other agroforestry
- Provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, hunting)
- Education
- Other
- Protection against natural hazard (e.g., floods, avalanches, rockfall)
- Protection against natural hazards (e.g. floods, avalanches, rock falls)
- Education
- Others

Other, please specify

Objective 5:

- Timber production
- Nature protection
- Pollution control (water, air and soil)

- Erosion control
- Water provision
- Climate change mitigation by carbon storage in biomass
- Biodiversity & habitat for wildlife
- Grazing and other agroforestry
- Provision of non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, hunting)
- Education
- Other
- Protection against natural hazard (e.g., floods, avalanches, rockfall)
- Protection against natural hazards (e.g. floods, avalanches, rock falls)
- Education
- Others

Other, please specify

Part 1: Ecological Changes

In the following, we visually present you projected **climate changes specific to your region from 2020 until 2100**. Hereby, we focus on the three most widely-used climate data predictions that represent an optimistic, intermediate and pessimistic change in climate. A detailed description of the scenarios as well as the sources of the underlying data can be found [here](#).

The data is presented in graphs: The horizontal axis is the time in years. The vertical axis shows the specific value (rain, temperature, drought). The orange area presents the range of the future predictions of all three scenarios combined. To outline the optimistic and pessimistic case we present the extreme values for the years 2030, 2050, 2080 and 2100 as a percentage change relative to the year 2020.

Please indicate in the following **how you understand** these changes and how they might affect the forest in your region. There is no 'right' or 'wrong' answer, we value your individual opinion.

Figure 1: Annual amount of rain

Regarding the changes in rainfall (figure 1), please provide your opinion on changes of the forest in your region for the further course of the 21 century:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* I expect an increase in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect an increase in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a change in species composition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 2: Average annual daily temperature

Regarding the changes in average temperature (figure 2), please provide your opinion on changes of the forest in your region for the further course of the 21 century:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* I expect an increase in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect an increase in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a change in species composition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 3: Longest annual drought period

Regarding the changes in drought period (figure 3), please provide your opinion on changes of the forest in your region for the further course of the 21 century:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* I expect an increase in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in forest productivity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect an increase in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in tree mortality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a change in species composition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Considering the above information about the changing climate in your region, what risk do you expect from the following threats to the forest in your region for the further course of the 21st century?

	No risk	Low risk	High risk	Very high risk	I do not know
* Forest fires	<input type="radio"/>				
* Drought damages	<input type="radio"/>				

* Storm damages	<input type="radio"/>				
* Flood damages	<input type="radio"/>				
* Snow damages	<input type="radio"/>				
* Pathogens & insects damages	<input type="radio"/>				
* Invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
* Regeneration & planting failure	<input type="radio"/>				

Please provide your opinion on the uncertainty of the provided information about climate change in your region.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is too high to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is high however it helps me to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Based on the provided information, what actions would you take to adapt the forest in your region to future impacts of climate change ?

	Highly increase	Increase	Stay the same	Decrease	Highly decrease	Not relevant	I do not know
* Share of mixed forest (broadleaves & conifers)	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of broadleaves	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of conifers	<input type="radio"/>						
* Species diversity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Assisted natural regeneration	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of native species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of non-native (exotic) species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of genetically modified species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Thinning intensity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Rotation age	<input type="radio"/>						
* Grazing intensity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Prescribed burning	<input type="radio"/>						

* Fertilization	<input type="radio"/>						
* Irrigation	<input type="radio"/>						
* Pesticides	<input type="radio"/>						

If you think that adaptation of the forest to future impacts of climate change is not relevant, please select the sentences that represent your opinion.

- The forest is already adapted to future impacts of climate change.
- Climate change impacts are low.
- The forest will adapt by itself.
- I have not enough information about what adaptation to do.
- I have other priorities regarding forest management.
- Climate change uncertainties are too high to take a decision.
- Other

Other, please specify:

* Do you think that the main problem in adapting the forest is a lack of financing?

- Yes, certainly
- Yes, probably
- No, probably
- No, certainly
- I do not know

* If you had only a limited amount of financing available, which of the above answered adaptation strategies would you prioritize for investment? Please select maximum three.

Maximum 3 selection(s)

- Share of mixed forest (broadleaves & conifers)
- Share of broadleaves
- Share of conifers
- Species diversity
- Assisted natural regeneration
- Planting of native species
- Planting of non-native (exotic) species
- Planting of genetically modified species
- Thinning intensity
- Rotation age
- Grazing intensity
- Prescribed burning
- Fertilization
- Irrigation
- Pesticides

Part 2: Socio-economic Changes

Similar to part 1, here we visually present you the **socio-economic changes that your region may experience from 2020 until 2100**. Hereby, we focus on the five most widely-used socio-economic change predictions that represent different global developments. We also present the optimistic, average and pessimistic changes, however they are not related to the cases of the climate change data. A detailed description of the scenarios as well as the sources of the underlying data can be found [here](#).

As in part 1, the data is presented in graphs: The horizontal axis is the time in years. The vertical axis shows the specific values. The orange area presents the range of the future predictions of all five scenarios combined. To outline the optimistic and pessimistic case we present the extreme values for the years 2030, 2050, 2080 and 2100 as a percentage change relative to the year 2020.

Please indicate in the following **how you understand** these changes and how they might affect the forest in your region. There is no 'right' or 'wrong' answer, we value your individual opinion.

Figure 4: Population

Regarding the changes in population (figure 4), please provide your opinion on changes in your region for the further course of the 21st century:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* I expect an increase in demand of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in demand of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect an increase in prices of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* I expect a decrease in prices of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect an increase in public funds (e.g., government, municipality).	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect a decrease in public funds (e.g., government, municipality).	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect an increase in forest activity costs (including labour).	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect a decrease in forest activity costs (including labour).	<input type="radio"/>					

Figure 5: Gross domestic product (GDP)

Regarding the changes in GDP (figure 5), please provide your opinion on changes in your region for the further course of the 21st century:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
* I expect an increase in demand of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect a decrease in demand of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I expect an increase in prices of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* I expect a decrease in prices of forest products.	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect an increase in public funds (e.g., government, municipality)	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect a decrease in public funds (e.g., government, municipality)	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect an increase in forest investments.	<input type="radio"/>					
* I expect a decrease in forest investments.	<input type="radio"/>					

Please provide your opinion on the uncertainty of the provided information about socio-economic change in your region.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is too high to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is high however it helps me to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Based on the provided information, what actions would you take in response to these socio-economic changes in your region?

	Highly increase	Increase	Stay the same	Decrease	Highly decrease	Not relevant	I do not know
* Share of mixed forest (broadleaves & conifers)	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of broadleaves	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of conifers	<input type="radio"/>						
* Thinning intensity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Rotation age	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing native species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing non-native (exotic) species	<input type="radio"/>						

In the following we present you projected wood price changes from 2020 to 2100 for your European level region (Mid-Western Europe). The information was obtained from a global land-use model, more information can be found [here](#).

The data is presented in the same style as the socio-economic changes.

Please consider these scenarios and inform us about what actions you would take as a response.

What actions would you take in response to these changes in price throughout the 21st century in your region?

	Highly increase	Increase	Stay the same	Decrease	Highly decrease	Not relevant	I do not know
* Share of mixed forest (broadleaves & conifers)	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of broadleaves	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of conifers	<input type="radio"/>						
* Thinning intensity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Rotation age	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing native species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing non-native (exotic) species	<input type="radio"/>						

Please provide your opinion on the uncertainty of the provided information about the price changes.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	I do not know
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is too high to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The uncertainties of the information, i.e. the range of possible changes, is high however it helps me to have an idea of what to expect for the future of the forest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Imagine the case that the forest in your region generates income through carbon payments for every ton of biomass it produces. In this case, what minimum carbon price (€ per ton of biomass produced) would you consider appropriate?

Based on the appropriate carbon price, how would you change your management to increase biomass production to generate income through carbon payments?

	Highly increase	Increase	Stay the same	Decrease	Highly decrease	Not relevant	I do not know
* Share of mixed forest (broadleaves & conifers)	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of broadleaves	<input type="radio"/>						
* Share of conifers	<input type="radio"/>						
* Thinning intensity	<input type="radio"/>						
* Rotation age	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing native species	<input type="radio"/>						
* Planting of fast-growing non-native (exotic) species	<input type="radio"/>						

Closing remarks

In order to improve the financing of adaptation of the forest to climate change and socio-economic change, what of the below listed additional financing would you consider?

- Government subsidy (including regional & municipal)
- Carbon payments for climate change mitigation
- Payments for regulating and maintenance services (e.g., flood protection, pollution control (air, water, soil), local climate control)
- Payments for non-timber forest products (e.g., mushrooms, berries)
- Forest insurance
- Tourism tax
- Voluntary donations (e.g., crowd funding, NGOs)
- Increase in timber harvest for financing
- Other

Other, please specify:

*What do you expect from scientists to support you in better understanding the provided information for adaptation planning and strategic decision making?

- Support better understanding of the future socio-economic changes
- Support better understanding of the future climate changes
- Support better understanding of the reliability of the information
- Simulate the impact of climate change on the forest with forest-growth-models
- Simulate different forest management strategies under climate change with forest-growth-models to give advice on what management to use to achieve adaptation
- Simulate different forest management strategies under socio-economic change (e.g., wood price) with forest-growth-models to give advice on what management to optimize revenues
- Simulate different tree species under climate change with forest-growth-models to give advice on what tree species to focus on
- Other

Other, please specify:

Choice experiment for risk aversion

This last part consists of a small game choice experiment that explores your risk aversion. Understanding individual risk aversion will help our research to comprehend decision making under climate change.

The choice experiment consists of 10 choices that are provided in the form of a gamble: For example, for choice 1 the two options have to be understood as follows:

- Option A: 9 chance in 10 (90%) to obtain 16€ and 1 chance in 10 (10%) to obtain 20€
- Option B: 9 chance in 10 (90%) to obtain 1€ and 1 chance in 10 (10%) to obtain 38.50€

Please, for each of the ten questions, indicate the preferred option with a mark on Option A or Option B.

	Option A	Option B
* A: 16€ (90%) or 20€ (10%) or B: 1€ (90%) or 38.50€ (10%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (80%) or 20€ (20%) or B: 1€ (80%) or 38.50€ (20%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (70%) or 20€ (30%) or B: 1€ (70%) or 38.50€ (30%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (60%) or 20€ (40%) or B: 1€ (60%) or 38.50€ (40%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (50%) or 20€ (50%) or B: 1€ (50%) or 38.50€ (50%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (40%) or 20€ (60%) or B: 1€ (40%) or 38.50€ (60%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (30%) or 20€ (70%) or B: 1€ (30%) or 38.50€ (70%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (20%) or 20€ (80%) or B: 1€ (20%) or 38.50€ (80%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 16€ (10%) or 20€ (90%) or B: 1€ (10%) or 38.50€ (90%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* A: 20€ (100%) or B: 38.50€ (100%)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Comments on the questionnaire

Here you can optionally write your comments on the questionnaire:

